

THE EFFECT OF WORK LOADS AND COMPENSATION ON WORK MOTIVATION IN SASMITA JAYA FOUNDATION

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ABSTRACT

The complexity of motivational problems has always been an obstacle to employee performance. Therefore, it is important to do research on the causal factors. To answer this problem, quantitative **approaches** and regression analysis are used. The population in this study were 70 employees of Sasmita Jaya Foundation and the sample technique used was census. The results prove that workload has a significant effect on work motivation with a regression coefficient of 0.569. Compensation has a significant effect on work motivation with a regression coefficient of 0.478. Simultaneous analysis prove that workload and compensation have a significant effect on work motivation with a determination coefficient of 72.5%, while the remaining 27.5% is explained by other variables outside of this study.

Keywords: Workload, Compensation, Work Motivation

PROEM

Compensation issues have always been an interesting conversation among Sasmita Jaya Group employees. The reason is, employees feel that the amount of compensation received at this time is not yet in accordance with the workload carried out. The workload in question is working hours that are valid for 12 hours and employees work on various tasks in each section. The employees do not apply, that the compensation received is in accordance with the UMP / UMR, but when compared with working hours and the number of tasks done, it seems there needs to be additional. Because ideally the minimum wage is given with 8 hours working hours, so that if there are excess hours it should be calculated overtime.

On various occasions, the employees have conveyed to the leadership. But the management ranks cannot do much, given the insignificant conditions and capabilities

of the foundation. As a result, all employees must be able to accept this situation gracefully.

Nevertheless, the foundation seeks to take concrete steps, for example involving employees to be involved in academic activities such as preparing a courtroom, seminar, training, proposal and so on. From there, are additional wages, which the foundation can give to employees.

The employees realize that the above efforts are quite helpful, but these activities are not always there every month, and not all employees can be included, so it remains a problem that is always a subject of conversation on every occasion. This condition greatly disrupts employee morale. Not infrequently, some employees come late, work carelessly, in a hurry and careless in their work, etc.

The series of problems, have an impact on the low level of discipline awareness, low performance, weak commitment and responsibility for the task, low creativity and innovation that all greatly disrupt the organization's overall performance. For example, poor academic services, many students complain about the lack of friendliness of academic staff in serving students, slow service, too many reasons and so on. This, if left unchecked, will make the image of the institution worse, so that the interest in college students decreases.

The results of research conducted by Anita, Aziz and Yunus (2013), Ningsih, Alwie and Fitri (2016) and Tiyasiningsih Indarti and Hendriani (2016) suggest that workload has a significant effect on motivation and performance. This finding confirms that the large number of jobs and high work risks will encourage employees to demand more, especially regarding rights. Employees also, do not hesitate to leave the organization if employees' rights are not granted within an unspecified period of time. As a result, the organization itself suffered losses.

The research results by Nugroho and Kunartinah (2012), Brahmasari and Suprayetno (2009), and Suwati (2013) suggest that compensation has a significant effect on work motivation. This finding confirms that compensation is an important factor in the rise and fall of employee morale. In fact, compensation is the main reason why people want to work. This is based on needs, and compensation is believed to be a factor that can fulfill it. So do not be surprised if there are some employees who are

willing to put their lives down, work late into the night, separate from their families, get rain and heat in order to get proper compensation.

THEORETIC

Workload

Workload, in the use of everyday language is often perceived as something unpleasant or negative connotation. Generally people perceive work pressure, the amount of responsibility, the number of jobs, the high risk of work and or the difficulty of a job. Therefore, almost most employees when faced with one of the workloads, tend to decrease morale, lack of enthusiasm, laziness and other bad things. Therefore in some research results, such as those conducted by Anita, Aziz and Yunus (2013) and Ningsih, Alwie and Fitri (2016) suggesting that the high pressure and the severity of the task is the reason why people are reluctant to take responsibility. Indeed this happens because of the low level of readiness of employees, both expertise readiness and mental readiness. But whatever it is, workload is one thing that must be minimized. for example by creating a management system, work processes using technology, system integrity and so forth.

Whereas according to Tiyasiningsih Indarti and Hendriani (2016) suggest, that workload has a significant effect on motivation. This finding confirms that the pressure, the number of jobs, the high risk and other negative things result in a decrease in employee motivation. Especially if a job has a difficult level of difficulty and coordination, it is not uncommon for employees to complain about the situation, resulting in low performance.

Compensation

According to Wahyudi (2018) compensation is all forms of work rights. In a study conducted by Nugroho and Kunartinah (2012), Brahmasari and Suprayetno (2009), and Suwati (2013) suggested that compensation has a significant effect on work motivation. The partial test results show that the compensation variable is the dominant factor influencing motivation. This finding firmly reinforces the theory that all forms of work rights such as salary / wages, incentives, bonuses, health support, performance allowances, severance / pension funds and or other non-financial compensation significantly affect employee morale. The impact of the compensation, reflected in the

form of expressions of attitude. For example the attitude of work morale, optimism, diligent attitude, hard work attitude and so forth, which then have an impact on the maximum work results.

In line with the above research, according to Firmandari (2014) and Tanjung (2005) suggest compensation has a positive and significant effect on work motivation. The analysis of these findings explains, that good compensation is able to influence employees, which by their own work motivation increases, adheres to and is disciplined, responsible, commitment to work, being kind to customers and so on.

Work Motivation

According to Wahyudi (2018) motivation means a sense of enthusiasm and encouragement of work enthusiasm. The sense of enthusiasm means to be born from within. Whereas encouragement, meaning spirit support provided by the organization and work environment or family. Often the motivation of giving birth to a miracle, which at first is difficult then becomes easy, which at first becomes problematic then becomes good, which at first is impossible then becomes possible, which at first is pessimistic then becomes optimistic, which initially becomes low then becomes high, and others so.

The interesting thing in terms of motivation is alternatives. When an organization or a leader does not have the ability to provide motivation from the material side, at least he realizes that attention and moral support are part of motivation. Many cases, where hunting is paid low, but the environment and family are the reason they remain patient and enthusiastic about the task.

Because this motivation is unique, so many experts carry out studies and analyzes that explain in detail what motivation is, how to motivate, why it is important to be motivated, whatever elements of motivation and so on. For example, motivation theory was developed by Abraham Maslow (1984), David Clarence McClelland (1961), Herzberg (1966), and Douglas McGregor (1960).

In addition, many results of research on motivation were also carried out, for example by Anita, Aziz and Yunus (2013), Ningsih, Alwie and Fitri (2016), Tiyasiningsih Indarti and Hendriani (2016), Nugroho and Kunartinah (2012), Brahmasari and Suprayetno (2009), Suwati (2013), Firmandari (2014) and Tanjung (2005).

METHOD

This research is included in the scope of Human Resource Management and the type of deductive research. The approach method used is a quantitative approach, so the research method is a causal associative method. According to Sugiyono (2012) the causal associative research method is research that aims to determine the effect of two or more variables, while the quantitative approach is used because the data in this study are expressed in numbers.

The quantitative approach according to Umar (2008), is an approach based on calculated data to produce a robust interpretation. Associative problems according to Sugiyono (2012), is a causal study that is a causal relationship. The analytical method used is multiple linear regression using SPSS software. The aim is to explain aspects that are appropriate or relevant to the observed phenomenon, and explain the characteristics of the phenomenon or problem that exists. The sampling technique used was simple randomization and determining the number of samples using Slovin formula. Methods of data collection by distributing questionnaires to 70 respondents directly and the measurement scale is a Likert scale. The data collected, then tabulated and obtained by SPSS for Windows software. The stages consist of validity test, reliability test, classic assumption test, partial test, simultaneous test and determinant test.

RESULT

Next below, the results of data processing, analysis and discussion will be displayed and the findings of a study are presented, and suggestions for improvement are also presented.

Table 1. Multiple Linear Regression Tests

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.835	4.730		.176	.861
	Workload	-.639	-.113	-.569	-5.666	.000
	Compensation	.807	.170	.478	4.760	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

Source: Research data, 2018

Table 2. Simultaneous tests

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	669.904	2	334.952	41.903	.000 ^a
	Residual	231.814	29	7.994		
	Total	901.719	31			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Workload, Compensation						
b. Dependent Variable: Motivation						

Source: Research data, 2018

Table 3. Determination Coefficient Test

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.862 ^a	.743	.725	2.827
a. Predictors: (Constant), Workload, Compensation				

Source: Research data, 2018

Based on the results of the data above, it can be stated the following explanation and analysis of the research:

1. The effect of workload on work motivation

Workload has a significant effect on work motivation with a regression coefficient of 0.569, the value of t -5.666 and a significance value of 0.000, it can be concluded H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This means that if the workload decreases by (-1) units then work motivation will increase by 0.569.

The analysis of the findings above is, if light work, minimal risk, minimal pressure and few in number, make employees more likely to work. Employees will show more motivation in every job. This finding has confirmed the theory and previous research that is true if workload has an impact on employee motivation. If the workload is high, the employee morale decreases. But conversely if the workload is low the morale goes up.

Therefore the foundation is expected to pay attention to the following bellow:

- a. Making Work Guidelines / SOP. HRD personnel make work guidelines or SOP and make a description and illustration of work technical that is easy to understand and can be applied. In addition, HRD also suggests the possibility of problems that occur in a job and suggests steps to resolve it.

Then the role of personnel personnel in conducting employee research is very useful for organizations.

- b. Placing wise leaders. Leaders can simplify the technicalities of complicated work to be adaptive and accompanied by examples of implementation.
 - c. Have an expert consultant. The existence of consultants, as people who are asked for their opinions in simplifying work, minimizing risks and how leaders are present as solutions.
 - d. Creating an integrated management system. The company makes a computerized based system so that work processes and problem solving are easier and faster.
 - e. Make a solid work team. Organizations create work teams that each employee has a good personality.
 - f. Strengthen work culture. The company delivers work values consistently on every occasion.
 - g. Creating a conducive work environment. The company provides convenient office facilities and governance.
2. The effect of compensation on work motivation

Compensation has a significant effect on work motivation with a regression coefficient of 0.478, a tcount of 4.760 and a significance value of 0.000, it can be concluded H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This means that if compensation increases by 1 unit then the work motivation of employees will increase.

The analysis of the findings above is true, that proper compensation can increase employee morale. Employees will show enthusiasm, passionate, optimistic and never give up so that they are always ready to do various tasks in all conditions. The impact of this is the birth of superior performance.

Therefore, it is recommended that the foundation be able to pay attention to the following:

- a. Provide basic salary according to UMP / UMR
- b. Provide health benefits (BPJS), performance benefits, bonuses and incentives according to labor legislation.
- c. Provide K3 equipment (Health, Safety and Occupational Safety).
- d. Give awards to outstanding employees.

- e. Organizing career paths fairly.
 - f. Providing training and education to potential employees.
3. The effect of workload and compensation on work motivation

Workload and compensation simultaneously have a significant effect on work motivation with a determination coefficient of 0.725, a calculated value of 41.903 and a significance value of 0.000, then it can be concluded H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This means that the existence of workload and compensation greatly impacts on employee morale (motivation). The findings above have confirmed the theory and previous research, which states that workload and compensation affect work motivation.

Based on the analysis and discussion above, the research findings can be presented as follows:

1. Workload has a significant effect on work motivation. This means that the foundation must strive, making a job easy to understand and easy to do, by making a work manual.
2. Compensation has a significant effect on work motivation. This means that the foundation must endeavor to provide employee rights as stipulated in the labor law.
3. Workload has a dominant influence on motivation. Foundations must make workload issues a priority in the organization.

CONCLUTION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion above, the research conclusions can be stated as follows:

1. Workload has a significant effect on work motivation with a regression coefficient of 0.569, the value of t -5.666 and a significance value of 0.000, then it can be concluded H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This means, if a job has a small level of risk, light and easy to do, a little pressure, the number of jobs a little and so on it can stabilize the emotional employee, who then born work morale, work enthusiasm, work optimism and so forth.
2. Compensation has a significant effect on work motivation with a regression coefficient of 0.478, a t count of 4.760 and a significance value of 0.000, then it

can be concluded H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. That is, if the foundation gives all employee rights properly as stipulated in labor legislation, including basic salary, incentives, bonuses, allowances and pension funds, the employee will feel happy, grateful and grateful that the mind, energy and time those who have been sacrificed have been paid fairly, so that a positive response from that is born of good attitude and work behavior.

3. Workload and compensation simultaneously have a significant effect on work motivation with a determination coefficient of 0.725, a calculated value of 41.903 and a significance value of 0.000, then it can be concluded H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. That is true, that workload and compensation have had an impact on employee motivation. If the workload is minimal and compensation is maximum, then the employee will bring his enthusiasm in every job. Employees show a happy and pleasant attitude, employees behave according to the SOP, and employees easily put out creative ideas.

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